

PREDICTING DELAMINATION GROWTH UNDER CYCLIC LOADING: AN APPROACH USING COMPUTATIONAL STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS AND TESTING

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ABSTRACT

For more brittle composites such as carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminates it is shown that criteria based on elastic fracture mechanics are an appropriate tool for predicting delamination growth under fatigue loading. The distribution of the local energy release rate along experimentally determined delamination fronts is obtained using the virtual crack closure method, implemented in a finite element analysis. Plots of measured delamination progression per load cycle versus computed energy release rate have been included in a Paris Law diagram as obtained experimentally using simple specimens for material characterization. The results lie well within the scatter band of the experimentally determined Paris Law.

INTRODUCTION

Motivated by the increasing use of composites also in primary structural components, research has been focussed on the disbond of two adjacent fibre reinforced layers of a laminate which is a prevalent state of damage commonly known as *delamination*. A recent survey on problems concerning composite parts of civil aircrafts [1] shows that delamination, mainly caused by impact, presents 60% of all kind of damage observed. Up to now failure caused by delamination is prevented by using empirically determined safety factors – based on maximum strain criteria – during construction and layout of components made of fibre reinforced materials. For an optimal utilisation of the potential offered by those materials as well as for the determination of inspection intervals however, it is essential to be able to predict delamination growth under cyclic loading.

In this investigation criteria based on fracture mechanics are used to describe the delamination failure. Propagation therefore is to be expected when a function of the mixed mode energy release rates G_I , G_{II} , G_{III} along the delamination front locally exceeds a certain value G_c . We suppose that G_c is a material property independent from geometry and stacking sequence, however, dependent on the ply orientation of the layers adjacent to the plane of delamination. The goal of the investigations presented is to obtain information on the dependence of delamination growth on the mixed mode energy release rates for cyclic loading

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and to verify the approach considered.

The specimens shown in Fig. 1, made of prepreg material (Ciba Geigy T300/914C), were designed to simulated specific different states of damage. The Configuration A type specimen with $[0_2/+45/0_2/-45/0/90]_S$ layup containing an artificial $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ square delamination at interface 3/4 was designed to simulate a structural component subject to fatigue loading which due to an impact has been damaged near the surface. An additionally introduced ply cut will serve to simulate fibre fracture. The specimen of Configuration B with a stacking sequence of $[\pm 2/\pm 45/\pm 45/\pm 88]_S$ and through the width cuts of both surface plies (plies 1 and 18) was designed to simulate a structural part with ply drops. Experiments with Configuration A specimens will provide input to set up a predictive model for delamination onset and growth. Additional experiments with Configuration B specimens will in the future serve for verification tests once the predictive model has been completed.

Figure 1: CFRE (Carbon Fibre Reinforced Epoxy) Specimens

COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS

In order to achieve correct results for mode separation when computing energy release rates the use of three-dimensional FE (Finite Element) models is required. A newly developed *layered element with eight nodes* formulated according to a continuum based three-dimensional shell theory [2] has been used for the three-dimensional models of the specimens. This element has been employed in order to reduce computing time, to prevent the elements from locking for small element thickness to element length ratios and to assure complete compatibility with the contactor and target elements to be used to avoid structural overlapping [3]. The most significant step for the current approach is the accurate computation of the distribution of the mixed mode energy release rates along arbitrarily shaped delamination fronts. It has been found that the virtual crack closure method is most favourable for the computation of energy release rates because the separation of the total energy release rate into the contributions by the different crack opening modes is possible in a straight forward manner [4]. When using this method only one FE-computation is necessary for a given delamination front which is beneficial especially when solving large geometrically non-linear problems. Preliminary investigations employing DCB and ENF specimens assured the reliability of the techniques used for computation of energy release rate distributions along straight and curved delamination fronts [5]. In addition, convergence studies for ENF and SLB specimens [6] did not show the non-convergence of the virtual crack closure method associated with the oscillatory singularity as reported in the literature, e. g. in [7, 8]. This may be due to very small bimaterial constants of the considered interfaces [9] or due to finite element meshes that are in the range of relatively constant results for G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} [8]. The issue will be investigated further.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

In preparation of the experimental part of the program, Configuration A specimens - as shown in Fig. 1 - have been cut from prefabricated plates made of prepreg material (T300/914C) with a stacking sequence of $[0_2/+45/0_2/-45/0/90]_S$. Artificial $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}$ square delaminations have been introduced at interface 3/4 during manufacturing by embedding a double foil of release film to simulate a pre-damaged structure. For the $R=0.1$ fatigue loading a frequency of 3 Hz was selected in order to avoid any heat generation which might alter the material behaviour. Stress maxima were chosen to be 30% of the ultimate tensile strength (UTS). For this setup delamination growth could not be observed even after several hundred thousand load cycles.

In order to induce even more severe damage and to force the delamination to grow the $[0]$ -ply directly beneath the deliberate delamination was damaged by a 10 mm cut through the fibres. Using C-scan for the detection, delamination growth was then observed at ply interface 4/5 while the deliberate delamination at interface 3/4 remained unaffected and did not start growing before the new delamination beneath had reached the same size and shape. At a stress level of 30% UTS no further delamination growth could be observed at all. Increasing the stress level to 40% and 50% UTS caused both delaminations to grow simultaneously.

COMPUTATION OF ENERGY RELEASE RATES

Seven delamination fronts - illustrated in Fig. 2 - have been selected for 3D-analysis, i.e. the starter front s_0 with an assumed delamination length of 0.2 mm and the fronts s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4 and s_7 which developed after 1,000 up to 7,000 load cycles respectively, further front s_∞ which developed after some 10,000 load cycles, after the growing delamination had reached the same size and shape as the artificial one above.

Figure 2: Delamination growth determined by C-scan after smoothing the delamination contours (one quarter of delaminated region shown)

Due to the structural unsymmetry of the geometrically symmetric specimen caused by the $\pm\alpha$ plies, models extending over the entire width of the specimen are necessary as shown in Fig. 3. The two top [0]-layers of the sublaminates have been grouped into one 3D-shell element, followed by one element which models the [45]-ply adjacent to the artificial square delamination. Two elements over the thickness were used for the cut [0]-layer, one for the [0]-ply to follow which is adjacent to the new growing delamination. The remaining 11 layers of the base laminate were joined into two elements of $[-45/0/90_2/0/-45]$ and $[0_2/+45/0_2]$ layup respectively. This configuration was used for the entire 3D investigation of all fronts. A penetration of the layers inside the delaminated regions was prevented by using a contact processor that utilizes a contactor target concept applying the penalty method [3]. Results show that the contact between the delaminated surfaces occurs only locally (Fig. 4), resulting in a mode I opening which had been neglected in previous 2D and 3D models [10].

Figure 3: Configuration A specimen, FE-model for front s_4

Figure 4: Detail of deformed geometry for front s_3

As an example the typical distribution of energy release rates along the growing front between plies 4/5 is shown in Fig. 5 for the situation after 3,000 load cycles. Energy release rates are evenly distributed along a considerable part of the growing front, with significant deviations only in the immediate vicinity of the ply cut ($s_3 = 0.25$ and $s_3 = 0.75$). A significant mode I contribution caused by a crack opening is noticeable. The total energy release rate $G_{tot} = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}$ is fairly constant along the entire front, its value being considerably higher than the experimentally obtained threshold values for delamination growth (G_{Ith} , G_{IIth}) so that delamination growth is to be expected along the entire front. Along the front of the deliberate delamination (interface 4/5) energy releases rates are far below the threshold values so that the contour is expected to remain constant. These results are in excellent agreement with experimental observations.

Figure 5: Distribution of energy release rates along the growing front s_3 (interface 4/5) after 3,000 load cycles

Summarizing, the total energy release rates are fairly constant along the entire front of the propagating delamination, dropping progressively with growing delamination as shown in Fig. 6. Mode I contribution decreases until it finally becomes negligible for front s_∞ . Comparing the results to those obtained using the quarter model [10] we notice a remarkable difference concluding that the unsymmetry caused by the ± 45 plies has to be taken into account, yielding the necessity of a full width model. Additionally it becomes obvious that simply suppressing any mode I contribution to avoid layer interpenetration is insufficient and contact analysis becomes essential to catch the local behaviour of cut and delaminated plies.

COMPARISON WITH PARIS LAW

Mode I and mode II failure under cyclic loading conditions have been characterized for the material of interest [11]. For mode I characterization unidirectional DCB specimens were tested under $R=0.1$ loading. Commonly known unidirectional ENF specimens and TCT (Transverse Crack Tension) specimens developed at DLR-Braunschweig were used under $R=0.1$ loading for mode II characterization. Threshold energy release rates in both cases

were defined as those values which would cause the delamination to grow 1 mm after one million load cycles ($da/dN \leq 10^{-6}$). These values have also been used in all of the previous diagrams. The results for mode I and mode II characterization were combined into one plot yielding Fig. 7.

Figure 6: Distribution of energy release rates G_{tot} along growing fronts s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4 and s_7

Due to the fact that for specimens of Configuration A delamination growth occurs between two 0° -plies, plots of measured delamination progression per load cycle (da/dN -values) versus computed total energy release rates along the fronts considered can be included in the above Paris Law diagram as shown in Fig. 8. For a front progressing from s_k to s_n the energy release rates used in the Paris Law plot were those obtained for the starter front s_k . Another possibility would be taking the average value from the computed energy release rates for front s_k and front s_n . Computational results lie well between the experimentally determined straight lines for mode I and mode II failure, the points with small mixed mode ratio r being closer to the failure line for mode II. The influence of the mixed mode ratio r on the location of points between the two Paris Law lines has to be investigated further.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The application of elastic fracture mechanics criteria has been tested as a possible tool for predicting delamination growth under tension-tension fatigue loading. This approach requires the accurate knowledge of the distribution of the local energy release rates along the contour of an arbitrarily grown delamination. The virtual crack closure method has been found most favourable for computation of mixed mode energy release rates in connection with finite element modeling employing a layered 3D shell element.

Cyclic loading experiments with Configuration A specimens show that measured delamination progression fits into a Paris Law as obtained experimentally using simple specimens for material characterization. Computations using delamination fronts from Configuration B and in addition from a delamination buckling specimen are in progress.

Due to the observed mixed mode conditions, Mixed Mode Bending (MMB) tests become necessary to determine Paris Law for mode mix, (e.g. $r = 0.3, r = 0.5$ and $r = 1.0$) for a verification of the approach. In addition to the fracture toughness characterization using specimens of unidirectional layup a test program is necessary in order to be able to characterize fracture toughness for interfaces with multidirectional layup [12].

Figure 7: Paris Law from material tests

Figure 8: Results obtained for Configuration A type specimens in comparison to Paris Law from material tests

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